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Tashkent Medical Academy, Tashkent, Uzbekistan**REACTIVE CHANGES IN THE AORTA IN EXPERIMENTAL METABOLIC SYNDROME**

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 <http://dx.doi.org/10.5281/Zenodo.11301137>**ABSTRACT**

The fundamental nature of the morphological changes in the pathogenesis of the metabolic syndrome and the area from which the initial changes develop, as well as many unresolved pathomorphogenetic aspects. A high-calorie diet throughout life is considered one of the main causes of metabolic syndrome. In understanding the pathogenesis of metabolic syndrome and hypodynamia, it is important to know the morphological changes observed in these pathologies. Changes in the trunk arteries in hypergravity, changes in hot climates have been studied. Taking into account the above, we studied the morphological changes in elastic type arteries as an object of research. In the obtained results, the main morphological substrate was the changes in the appearance of destructive and defragmentation in the fibrous structures of the vascular wall of the elastic type.

Key words: morphology, elastic vessels, metabolic syndrome.

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Toshkent tibbiyot akademiyasi**TAJRIBAVIY METABOLIK SINDROMDA AORTANING REAKTIV O'ZGARISHI****ANNOTATSIYA**

Metabolik sindrom patogenezidagi morfologik o'zgarishlarning fundamental tabiati va dastlabki o'zgarishlar qaysi sohadan kelib chiqishi, shuningdek, hal qilinmagan ko'plab patomorfogenetik jihatlar. Hayot davomida yuqori kaloriyali parhez metabolik sindromning asosiy sabablaridan biri

hisoblanadi. Metabolik sindrom va gipodinamiya patogenezini tushunishda ushbu patologiyalarda kuzatilgan morfologik o'zgarishlarni bilish muhimdir. Gipergravitatsiyada magistral arteriyalardagi o'zgarishlar, issiq iqlimdagi o'zgarishlar o'rganildi. Yuqoridagilarni hisobga olgan holda biz tadqiqot obyekti sifatida elastik tipdagi arteriyalardagi morfologik o'zgarishlarni o'rgandik. Olingan natijalarda asosiy morfologik substrat elastik tipdagi tomir devorining tolali tuzilmalarida destruktiv va defragmentatsiya ko'rinishidagi o'zgarishlar bo'ldi.

Kalit so'zlar: morfologiya, elastik tomirlar, metabolik sindrom.

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РЕАКТИВНОЕ ИЗМЕНЕНИЕ АОРТЫ ПРИ ЭКСПЕРИМЕНТАЛЬНОМ МЕТАБОЛИЧЕСКОМ СИНДРОМЕ

АННОТАЦИЯ

Фундаментальность морфологических изменений в патогенезе метаболического синдрома и область, из которой развиваются начальные изменения, а также многие нерешенные патоморфогенетические аспекты. Высококалорийная диета на протяжении всей жизни считается одной из основных причин метаболического синдрома. Для понимания патогенеза метаболического синдрома и гиподинамии важно знать морфологические изменения, наблюдаемые при этих патологиях. Изучены изменения магистральных артерий в условиях гиперgravитации, изменения в условиях жаркого климата. Учитывая вышеизложенное, нами были изучены морфологические изменения артерий эластического типа как объекта исследования. В полученных результатах основным морфологическим субстратом явились изменения деструктивных и дефрагментационных волокнистых структур сосудистой стенки эластического типа.

Ключевые слова: морфология, эластические сосуды, метаболический синдром.

Relevance of the problem: According to the World Health Organization, about 60% of the world's population has a low level of physical activity for their lifestyle. As a result of a lifestyle caused by inactivity, 1.9 million deaths are observed in the literature. A decrease in physical activity causes the metabolism of all substances in the body to deviate from the norm (2,3,5,6). Over time, changes begin to develop in the organs of the cardiovascular, respiratory, musculoskeletal and endocrine systems (1,7,9,10,14). The fact that the development of hypodynamia is the cause of the metabolic syndrome is presented in many literatures. Metabolic syndrome causes a number of metabolic disorders that increase the risk of developing cardiovascular pathologies and diabetes. The pathogenesis of metabolic syndrome is complex and involves many unsolved problems. When the diameter of blood vessels decreases, the speed of blood flow also decreases. It is estimated that 10% to 15% of the total blood volume is in the arterial circulatory system. This feature of high systemic pressure and low volume is characteristic of the arterial system. There are two main types of arteries in the body: elastic arteries and muscular arteries. Muscular-type arteries include those with anatomical names such as the brachial artery and the femoral artery. Muscular arteries have more smooth muscle cells in their intima than elastic arteries. Elastic-type arteries are the arteries closest to the heart (aorta and pulmonary arteries) and contain more elastic tissue in their intima than muscular-type arteries. This property of elastic type arteries allows to maintain a constant pressure gradient against them despite the constant contractile (pumping) effect of the heart (4,12,13).

Materials and methods of research. Mature white laboratory rats weighing 180-200 grams were used as study material. The white rats taken for the experiment were divided into 2 groups.

There were 15 rats in each group. For morphological research, the elastic type of thoracic aorta was taken, and the histological sections prepared on a rotor microtome with a thickness of 8-10 microns were stained with hematoxylin and eosin, Van Gison, and Weigert methods.

The first group was the control group, 10 rats without clinical signs of somatic and infectious diseases were taken. Rats in the control group were continuously fed a conventional diet with free food and water ad libitum.

In our second group, we released an experimental metabolic syndrome model. Healthy rats, after denying signs of infectious and somatic diseases, were given a diet rich in fat and carbohydrates. The diet of rats is 60% laboratory feed, 20% sheep fat, 20% fructose. A 20% solution of fructose was given instead of drinking water. Rats were euthanized 60 and 90 days after the experiment.

Laboratory white rats in the control and experimental groups were kept in the same conditions of the vivarium. The body weight of laboratory white rats in the control and experimental groups was measured. Also, blood glucose, insulin, triacylglycerol, total cholesterol, LPNP, LPVP are determined. In order to determine the inflammatory process, the total amount and morphological composition of leukocytes were determined. G.G. Avtandilov method and NanoZoomer (REF C13140-21.S/N000198/HAMAMATSU PHOTONICS /431-3196 JAPAN) Hamamatsu (QuPath-0.4.0, NanoZoomer Digital Pathology Image) morphometric computer program are used for conducting morphometric examinations. The obtained data were determined in the statistical section of Microsoft Excel 2010 as the arithmetic mean M , the average error of the relative sizes m , and the accuracy coefficient t . Photomicrographs of histological preparations were captured using a CX40 model OD400 camera microscope.

Results and discussion. Under the conditions of hypodynamia called in the experimental conditions, metabolic disorders were mainly manifested in various forms of metabolism in blood vessels. As a result of metabolic disorders, fatty spots of various forms are detected in the intima of the main blood vessels, especially around the abdominal part of the aorta and the network of vessels. In rats, induced metabolism and hypodynamia were found to increase macroscopically body weight in groups fed a high-calorie diet. The average weight of the rats taken for the experiment was 174.25 ± 10.55 grams, and on the 30th and 60th days of the experiment, this indicator increased to 214.15 ± 8.35 grams. It was found that the increase in body weight was followed by an increase in internal organs and blood vessels mainly by fatty deposits. This means that in the morphological studies, all internal organs, including the main blood vessels, depending on the type, in the elastic type vessels, lipodosis in the form of the initial stage of atherosclerosis, changes in the form of liposclerosis, destructive, elastolysis in elastic fibers. changes are detected (Picture 1).

In our study, mucoid mucus and fatty spots are detected in the intima of the aortic vessel. When stained with hematoxylin and eosin, no drastic changes were detected on the surface of the aortic vessel endothelium, a small number of foamy cells were detected in the subendothelial layer.

1-Picture. Rat sample- 5. The arch of the aorta. Lipid spots and foci of liposclerosis are identified on the inner surface. In the subendothelial layer, a collection of vesicular cells is identified. Paint G.E. The size is 10×10 .

2-Picture. Rat sample-3. The arch of the aorta. Liposclerosis and chaotic arrangement of fibrous structures on the surface of the endothelium. Unevenness of the endothelial layer, foci of endotheliosis are determined. Paint G.E. The size is 20×10

At the same time, a slight thickening of the basement membrane of the subendothelial layer, swellings in the interstitial tissue and foci of inflammation in fibrous structures, and a large number of infiltration of macrophages and lymphocytes around it are detected. An unevenness of the endothelium layer occurs, and it is determined that increased mechanical friction under the influence of hemodynamic flow has developed in the form of lesions on the surface of the endothelium layer. In fact, severe damage to the endothelial layer during mechanical friction is manifested in the form of endotheliosis foci, and foci of platelet aggregations are determined on the exposed surfaces (Picture 2). Atrophic and focal hypertrophic changes were detected in sparsely located muscle cells of the vascular middle layer.

3-Picture. Rat sample - 7. Abdominal part of the aorta. Liposclerosis and chaotic arrangement of fibrous structures on the surface of the endothelium. In the subendothelial layer, histiocytes, a small number of infiltration of lymphocytes. Paint G.E. The size is 40×10.

4-Picture. Rat sample-2. Section of the aortic arch. Raised liposclerosis on the surface of the endothelium (1) has a uniform muscular and fibrous appearance in the middle layer, interstitial edema is detected in the interval (2). Paint G.E. The size is 20×10

It is determined that there is an increase in sparse and rough fibrous connective tissue around the atrophically changed muscle cells. Precisely, the morphofunctional pathogenetic aspect of these changes in the vessel wall, under the influence of the pulse pressure in the vessel cavity, causes the vibro-vibration in the branching areas of the vessels and a sharp violation of the surface elastic resistance of the vessel under the influence of the turbulent flow and internal circulation flow. These hemodynamic changes are associated with the accumulation of lipid stains on the inner surface of the vessel through metabolic disturbances. As a result, it is determined that the destructive changes of fibrous structures in the vascular intima and middle layer continue with the accumulation of intermediate products (Picture 3).

In the middle layer, the increase of interstitial swelling and coarse fibrous connective tissue, the proliferation and infiltration of focal fibroblasts and macrophages in these places, deform the vessel wall and the possibility of bulging of the intima surface and the accumulation of lipid deposits. leads to an increase disorders, are the descending and abdominal parts of the aorta. (Picture 4).

5-Picture. Rat sample-3. Section of the aortic arch. On the surface of the intima, there are foci of endotheliosis (1), swellings of different appearance in the interval, a rough fibrous landscape is determined in the middle layer (2). Paint G.E. The size is 20×10

It is determined that most lipid stains have improved in the ascending and descending aorta. It is determined that the elimination of these fatty stains by macrophages from inside the vessel and the accumulation of macrophages in the subendothelial layer of the vessel wall led to the formation of a foamy layer or a layer composed of foamy cells (Picture 5). As a result of hypodynamia and derailment of metabolism in rats, it was macroscopically determined that the intensity of deposition of lipids of different densities in the blood plasma on the vessel surface, or the most concentrated areas of the aorta in metabolic

Conclusion.

1. It was found that most of the lipid deposits in the wall of the aorta from the trunk vessels of rats with metabolic syndrome were accumulated on the intima surface. This is a factor in the development of atherosclerosis.

2. In the case of hypodynamia in the metabolic syndrome, it was found that massive lipid spots were accumulated to a greater extent than usual in most of the ascending and bifurcating areas of the aorta, except for the descending and abdominal areas.

3. It was found that a large number of vesicular cells increased and accumulated in the intima and middle layers of the aorta. It was found that this, in turn, continued with the development of the process of mechanical friction and damage in hypodynamic flow, raising the inner surface of the vessel from its plane.

4. It was found that there was an increase in connective tissue with collagen fibers and an uneven thickening of the vessel wall between the middle and inner layers of the aorta.

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9 ЖИЛД, 2 СОН

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